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Simplified Vareststraint test for analyzing weldability of Nickel Superalloys

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Abstract

High temperature Ni-base superalloys are largely used in components of aircraft engines which are subjected to high thermal (above 700°C) and structural loads. Investment casting has been traditionally implemented for the manufacturing of these components with different levels of complexity and size. However, investment casting of large and complex parts can entail some difficulties which lead to higher casting defect ratios and the need of repairing. Therefore, it is essential to develop easy to repair Ni superalloys castings, i.e., castings with an enhanced weldability or reduced weld cracking susceptibility. Improvement of weldability will also enable the combination of small size castings with forged and rolled components in welded structures reducing overall manufacturing costs and foundry capacity requirements.

Cracking susceptibility of Ni superalloys castings is much greater in comparison with equivalent wrought components due to coarser and non-homogeneous microstructures, grain boundary segregations and particular chemistry which promote several cracking mechanisms during welding. A methodology based on Vareststraint test (hot cracking test) is introduced to evaluate cracking susceptibility of Ni superalloys with a reduced number of samples. This reduction is particularly important when considering castings since practical conclusions can be drawn with minimum material sampling. Influence of Vareststraint testing parameters, machine performance and total crack length (TCL) measurement procedure on scattering of results are assessed. Conditions to reduce scattering and improve repeatability and reproducibility of results are defined, which are essential to compare weldability performance between different alloys and microstructures.

Keywords: Ni superalloys, Weldability, Hot cracking, Vareststraint, Solidification cracking, HAZ cracking.

Introduction

Nickel base superalloys were developed with the purpose to work in corrosive environments and high temperature conditions maintaining their tensile, fatigue and creep properties [1][2]. First precipitation-strengthened Ni-base superalloys were strengthened by precipitation of γ' (Ni_3Al , Ni_3Ti and $\text{Ni}_3(\text{Ti}, \text{Al})$) but they underwent severe strain age cracking (SAC) after welding and post weld heat treatment. In order to avoid SAC, in 1963, Inconel 718 alloy was developed with outstanding mechanical properties thanks to the excess of Nb in the matrix which forms metastable γ'' precipitates of Ni_3Nb . The precipitation kinetics of γ'' is slower compared to γ' which contributes to the improvement of weldability and resistance to SAC [2]. Since its development, it is well known the appropriate properties of this alloy for the manufacturing of high responsibility hot section parts of aerospace gas turbines [1][2].

Precipitation-strengthened Ni-base alloys are composed by austenite matrix with secondary and intermetallic phases such as NbC and Laves phases. These last two phases are present in IN718 as a result of segregation on castings and welds [3]. Due to the metastable nature of γ'' precipitate, IN718 alloy is used for temperature service until 650 °C. Above this temperature γ'' phase is replaced by δ phase which reduces creep resistance, ductility and weldability.

Wrought and rolled IN718 are considered weldable alloys, however severe cracking can be obtained when working with equivalent casting parts. The cracking mechanisms frequently observed in welds in IN718 alloy, are the heat affected zone (HAZ) liquation cracking [4][5][6][7][8][9] and solidification cracking in the fusion zone (FZ). HAZ liquation cracking is caused primarily by the constitutional liquation of Laves phase and carbide precipitates in the grain boundaries, liquation of δ phase and by coarse microstructures in the HAZ [5][10][11][12]. Some studies revealed that the solution annealing reduces the susceptibility to this kind of cracking in IN718 while ageing heat treatments promotes it [6][7][13][14][15][16][17]. Moreover solidification cracking occurs due to the formation of γ/NbC and γ/Laves constituents in the interdendritic zones as a result of segregation of chemical elements. This segregation occurs due the presence of residual elements like B, C and Zr or impurities (P and S which must be kept as low as possible), low interstitial element like Si, or combinations of Nb and C. Residual stresses, solidification shrinkage and weld pool size also influences the susceptibility to this cracking mechanism [18].

The authors of this paper are currently involved in a research project trying to improve the weldability of IN718 investment castings [19]. For that reason it is important to settle a hot cracking susceptibility assessment trial which can evaluate weldability improvements and conclude on significant weldability differences between casting samples with different chemical compositions, casting conditions or heat treatments.

Weldability is usually defined as the material resistance to cracking during fabrication. Thus, a material that has good weldability will be resistant to various forms of cracking during welding. Different tests have been previously developed to compare and quantify weldability. In this context, V-restraint test was designed in 1960s by Savage and Lundin in order to evaluate hot cracking susceptibility due to metallurgical variables of a material [20][21][1][22]. The basic test is the longitudinal one which consists in the application of a bending deformation along the length of the weld. It uses several interchangeable die blocks to produce specific augmented strains that lead to different amount of cracking in both FZ and HAZ. Cracks are measured and the sum of all them gives the total crack length (TCL), forming a curve that quantitatively represents the weldability for a material.

Figure 1. Schematic view of the Varestraint test [23].

Nowadays there are several modifications of the original test. Despite there is an international standard covering the application of this test, there are many testing conditions which are not fully imposed [24]. Test results can be used to compare and rank alloys in the same machine, but trends may not be fully reproducible in different ones. Also the measurement procedure is performed in a different way in different labs [21].

Moreover, this test has an inherent variability which is particularly high for castings due to their inhomogeneous microstructure. The behavior of the machine (stroke rate,...), the selected welding and testing parameters and the TCL measurement procedure itself also contribute to result variability. In a recent paper this was nicely investigated [21].

In this work, an evaluation of a testing procedure for the study of the weldability of nickel superalloys is provided. The reliability of this assessment methodology is tested by comparing results obtained of rolled IN718 with different TCL measurement procedures, different testing machines and synchronization methods. Critical issues related to optimum testing conditions, machine and TCL measurement repeatability and their influence on result scattering are discussed. The reduction of this scattering is vital in order to identify statistically significant differences between material batches.

Experimental procedure

In this study plates of rolled IN718 alloy were used for testing weldability assessment methodology. Chemical composition of tested alloy is included in Table 1. Rolled material fulfilled the standard AMS 5596 and it was in the solution annealed state ($995\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$).

Table 1. Chemical composition of wrought Inconel 718 alloy in wt. %.

Al	B	C	Co	Cr	Cu	Fe	Mn	Mo	Ni	P	S	Si	Ti	Nb	Ta
0.54	0.004	0.052	0.46	18.4	0.05	18.8	0.23	3.09	52.2	0.009	<0.002	0.09	1.00	5.03	<0.05

The metallographic preparation for the microstructure analysis of base material and welds, consisted of polishing the previously mounted sample with diamond suspension up to 1 micron particle size. After that the samples were chemically etched with Kalling's reagent. The microstructure was observed in the FEG-SEM (ZEISS Ultra Plus Field Emission) and in the light microscope (Olympus GX 51).

The weldability of this material was tested in a home-made Varestraint testing device at IK4-LORTEK facilities (Figure 22). The test bench was designed and manufactured by IK4-LORTEK and it complies

with the general requirements set by ISO/TR 17641-3 “Destructive tests on welds in metallic materials-Hot cracking tests for weldments-Arc welding processes-Part 3: Externally loaded tests”. The system is designed to work both with arc welding and laser beam welding equipment and different testing parameters (stroke rate, welding rate, synchronization set-ups...) can be selected.

The Varestraint system integrates a compact tooling for application of bending deformation during test. It is composed by a mandrel and two rolls which rotate without restraint (Figure 22).

Figure 2. a) Mandrel and rolls for the sample testing. b) Varestraint bench and welding torch attached to the robot.

The Varestraint test bench at IK4-LORTEK is also composed by a hydraulic system of a maximum load of 80 KN controlled by a high precision servovalve to perform an accurate movement of the cylinder. The response time at the highest stroke rate of 150 mm/s is only 0.03 seconds which is equivalent to 4.5 mm. This is observed in Figure 33, where commanded stroke during deformation time is compared with real signal from servovalve.

Figure 3. Response of the hydraulic system at the maximum stroke rate (150 mm/s).

In conventional Varestraint test different augmented strains are applied using different mandrel radii according to the following equation.

$$\varepsilon = \frac{t}{2 \cdot R} \times 100$$

Being ε the augmented strain in %, t the thickness of the sample in mm and R de radio of the mandrel in mm.

In the current work, augmented strains of 2, 4 and 8% were applied, using different mandrels. The goal was to try to evaluate and rank cracking susceptibility using only these 3 levels of deformation. Vareststraint testing samples with 150 x 50 x 3.2 mm dimensions were cut by laser-cutting from 3.2 mm thickness rolled plates. Two expendable support plates of 304 stainless steel are accurately located in both sides of the sample in each test to avoid kinking and to force the sample to adapt to the mandrel during the deformation. The dimensions of these support plates were 150 mm in length, 10 mm in width and 3 mm in thickness.

The welding technology used for this test was GTAW and concretely TIGSpeed 352 Synergic RCHW model from EWM brand. Autogenous welding, i.e., without filler metal, was applied using the welding parameters shown in Table 2222.

Table 2. Welding parameters used for Vareststraint tests.

Ws (mm/s)	Current (A)	Voltage (V)	Heat input (J/mm)	Arc lenght (mm)	Electrode tip angle (°)
1	70	9.25	648	2	30

Obtained cracks for each augmented strain were evaluated by optical microscopy after polishing with 3 μ m of diamond suspension and electroetching by oxalic acid (10 %) with 3V.

Results

Characterization of the base material

An equiaxed microstructure is observed in the base metal, rolled IN718 alloy. There is a significant presence of twins, which is a common feature in this type of austenitic superalloys [25]. The presence of niobium carbides was detected by EDS microanalysis (Figure 44).

Figure 4. Microstructure obtained for the rolled material. a) Equiaxed grains with presence of twins. b) NbC precipitates

The grain size measured is 29 μ m, corresponding to a grade G7 ASTM. A representative micrograph is shown in Figure 55.

Figure 5. Microstructure obtained for the grain size determination 20x.

The autogenous weld bead achieved with selected welding parameters is shown in Figure 66. The width of the fusion zone at the face was approximately 8 mm and full penetration was obtained with minimum reinforcement in the root.

Figure 6. Autogenous weld bead achieved with selected welding parameters.

Varestraint test results

In order to develop a simplified weldability assessment methodology for an accurate hot cracking evaluation, 9 samples of IN718 rolled were evaluated only at three different augmented strains: 2, 4 and 8% with 10 mm/s stroke rate. The influence of the measurement procedure of the TCL was evaluated to assess the best measurement procedure which leads to minimum measurement error. For this purpose, cracking of 9 samples were evaluated with two proposed procedures using different objectives which provide different magnifications in the microscope (Leica DVM6). In both objectives, the lighting was homogeneous and was emitted through a ring of LED lights. The two procedures used for the evaluation of the cracking are:

- Procedure A: low magnification objective up to 50X magnification
- Procedure B: high magnification objective at 150X magnification

Measurements of the average of TCL and the standard deviation obtained by both procedures with identical samples are represented in Figure 77.

Figure 7. TCL representation as function of augmented strain for Procedure A and B.

Graph shows that TCL and standard deviation are higher if low magnification objective is used. Numerical values and the source of this difference are explained later on.

With the aim to analyze the repeatability of the measurement, one sample of each augmented strain was evaluated 5 times according to Procedure B. The obtained standard deviation was smaller than 7 % as can be seen in Table 33.

Table 3. Hot cracking values obtained from the evaluation of two samples 5 times.

Aug. strain (%)	Avg. TCL (mm)	StDev. TCL (mm)	StDev. TCL/Avg. TCL
2	12.9	0.9	7.3%
4	14.8	0.6	4.4%

The same Varestraint tests with the same material were performed in another testing machine to compare results and overall behavior. The same welding parameters were employed. Synchronization between welding and the application of deformation was not initially imposed in both machines.

A scheme of that synchronization is represented in the Figure 88. The application of the deformation can take place in different points of the welding. Deformation can be applied exactly when the welding torch passes the center point of the mandrel or slightly before making coincident the end of the deformation with the location of the welding torch at the center point.

Figure 8. Scheme of synchronization possibilities.

The performance of Varestraint tests and the cracking measurement procedures that were compared, are summarized as follows:

- IK4-LORTEK Procedure A: deformation starts in the center point. Measurement procedure at magnification up to 50X.
- IK4-LORTEK Procedure B: deformation starts in the center point. Measurement procedure at magnification of 150X.
- Machine 2 Procedure A: deformation finishes in the center point. Measurement procedure at magnification up to 50X.

Comparison of the TCL results obtained by IK4-LORTEK Vastrestraint test with both cracking measurement procedures and another external machine, named Machine 2 with Procedure A are shown in Figure 99.

Figure 9. TCL representation as function of augmented strain for two different machines.

Cracking obtained with Machine 2 Procedure A is much higher than the obtained by IK4-LORTEK Procedure B, however the values of IK4-LORTEK Procedure A are overlapped. Results are displayed in Table 444.

Table 4. Values obtained from the evaluation of hot cracking with different Vastrestraint machines and different procedures.

	Aug. strain (%)	Avg. TCL (mm)	StDev. TCL (mm)	StDev. TCL/Avg. TCL
IK4-LORTEK Procedure A		15.0	5.5	36.6%
IK4-LORTEK Procedure B	2	8.7	1.0	11.7%
Machine 2 Procedure A		18.8	3.3	17.6%
IK4-LORTEK Procedure A		23.3	4.5	19.2%
IK4-LORTEK Procedure B	4	15.1	1.4	9.1%
Machine 2 Procedure A		23.6	2.8	11.9%
IK4-LORTEK Procedure A		22.2	4.3	19.4%
IK4-LORTEK Procedure B	8	15.8	1.9	12.3%
Machine 2 Procedure A		21.9	2.9	13.4%

Since both machines used different synchronization criteria, another set of tests with different synchronization setup was performed at IK4-LORTEK's Vareststraint machine in order to evaluate its influence in the hot cracking. Two different synchronizations requirement were studied:

- Deformation starting in the center point.
- Deformation finishing in the center point.

For the second case, the deformation triggering point was calculated. Considering the selected welding parameters and particularly welding speed the run required to complete deformation were 2 and 3.5 mm for 4 and 8% augmented strains, respectively. In Table 563 the performed tests are summarized.

Table 5. Synchronization between the welding and application of the deformation.

Set of parameters	Application of deformation from the center point (mm)	Aug strain (%)
1	0	8
2	3.5	8
3	0	4
4	2.0	4

Table 674 shows for both augmented strains, that the TCL is greater when the application of the deformation finishes in the center of the mandrel. The standard deviation in all cases is below 12 %. These results suggest that the synchronization affects the formation of cracks.

Table 6. Values of hot cracking obtained for two synchronization methods for each augmented strain measured with Procedure B.

Deformation	Aug. strain (%)	Avg. TCL (mm)	StDev. TCL (mm)	StDev. TCL / Avg. TCL
Starts in the center point	4	15.1	1.4	9.1%
Finishes in the center point		30.8	1.2	3.8%
Starts in the center point	8	15.8	1.9	12.3%
Finishes in the center point		19.0	1.4	7.4%

The maximum crack length also reveals larger cracks when the deformation finishes in the center point of the mandrel (Table 788).

Table 7. Average of MCL and standard deviations for 4 % of augmented strain for different synchronization methods.

Deformation	Aug. strain (%)	Avg. MCL (mm)	StDev. MCL (mm)
Starts in the center point	4	1.8	0.8
Finishes in the center point		2.6	0.4

Discussion

As explained in the introduction, Vareststraint tests has been traditionally applied to study hot cracking susceptibility of nickel superalloy [21]. This is an effective test method to analyze solidification and liquation cracking in these alloys. However, a great scattering in the TCL is usually observed in the results obtained by this test which makes difficult the sorting of alloys and batches.

At the beginning of this work, the standard deviation obtained from 3 samples tested in the same condition was 36.6% of the mean value for the worst case (i.e., 2% augmented strain and up to 50X magnification for TCL measurement). For the same testing condition, but increasing the magnification, the standard deviation on the results for the same samples was reduced to 11.7%. The same great reduction on scattering was observed for samples tested at 4% and 8% when using this measurement procedure (procedure B) leading to TCL standard deviations 9.1% and 12.3% respectively (**Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**). Therefore, the TCL measurement procedure and the magnification employed are of great importance for the reliability of the results. It is worth noting that ISO/TR 17641-3:2005 standard suggest to examine cracks at a magnification of 25X which in the current study led to an enhanced variability on TCL [24]. According to current work, this magnification should be increased to 150X in order to reduce result variability. Next figure compares the cracks detected and measured in the same sample when completing the inspection of cracks at 50X and 150X. It can be observed that the greatest difference relies in the number of cracks interpreted in the FZ. No differences in the number of cracks detected in the HAZ were observed.

At 50X, 21 cracks were measured in total whereas at 150X this number was reduced to 18, with MCL of 2.74 mm and 1.68 mm respectively. Therefore, MCL can be more precisely determined at higher magnification since operator can decide better on the real starting and finishing points of cracks. As a consequence the TCL measured at the lowest magnification was comparatively much higher. This increase on TCL which is consistently observed in current work is also due to the misinterpretation of marks in the FZ which are not really open cracks if analyzed at high magnification (Figure 101012). Therefore, the operator is able to distinguish more clearly real cracks from other solidification marks (crests) in the weld bead when increasing magnification.

Figure 10 Cracks detected and measured in the same sample (2% augmented strain) at different inspection magnifications.

The increase of the inspection magnification ensures also the highest repeatability. This was demonstrated by measuring the same sample 5 times by the same operator (Table 5). The resulting ratio between Avg. TCL and StDev. TCL was 4.4 and 7.3% for the two samples (2 and 4% augmented strain, respectively) which can be considered as the minimum error introduced due to the measurement with this procedure (Procedure B).

Besides the measurement procedure, the synchronization has demonstrated to directly influence Vareststraint test results. As shown above (Table 674), much higher TCL was observed when the deformation was fully completed exactly when the TIG welding torch surpasses the center point of the specimen. The difference with the case at which the deformation starts just while welding the central point is huge, particularly for the case of 4% augmented strain. In this case, the Avg. TCL rises twofold and this is clearly observed just looking at the surface of tested samples (Figure 111113). Note that in this analysis, the Procedure B was applied and therefore a minimum scattering on the measurement of TCL was ensured for samples tested in

each condition. Reduced scattering in the measured average values from 3 tested samples also supports the robust and repetitive behavior of the Varestraint test system and confirms the important effect of synchronization. Fast, accurate and repetitive synchronization between welding run and deformation is usually considered as an important requirement of Varestraint test systems [20], but to the author's best knowledge there is not any relevant deep analysis on this matter. Concerning speed and accuracy, the Varestraint system used in this study is equipped with a fast servovalve, advanced control system and pressure accumulator which provides a response time of 0.03 s to reach required stroke rate during the deformation stage and since the triggering signal is received from target welding torch position.

As it is shown in Figure 111113, there were clear larger cracks in the FZ of samples tested with anticipated synchronization. i.e., when deformation finishes exactly while the TIG torch goes by the central point of the testing sample. Note that this central point is highlighted on the pictures of tested samples in Figure 111113. For the anticipated condition, total crack length rises to 30.8 mm whereas for the deformation in the center point the TCL is 15.1 mm (Table 674). Moreover average maximum crack length (Avg. MCL) was much longer (2.6 mm) in comparison with the other synchronization setup (1.8 mm) (Table 788).

Figure 11 Photo of the surface of two samples tested at 4% augmented strain with different synchronization setups. At the left hand side sample deformation finishes in the center whereas at the right hand side deformation starts at the center.

Both higher Avg. TCL and Avg. MCL for the anticipated synchronization can be explained as follows. Considering that melt pool has a given size which is dependent on heat input resulting from welding parameters (intensity, voltage and welding speed) the relative positioning of melt pool while applying the deformation (stroke) will affect the induced FZ cracking. If the melt pool is mainly before the central point during deformation, that means that a high volume of weld material within this testing area (between the start of deformation and the central point) will be in the liquid state. Therefore, solidification on this area

will be coincident with application of full deformation and solidification cracking will be enhanced in the FZ.

On the contrary, if the melt pool is exactly at the central point, there will be a lower amount of material in the same so-called testing area in liquid state. This is because the material in this area will have been solidified by the time the deformation is started. Therefore, FZ cracking will not be so critical even if the same deformation is induced during Varestraint test.

It must be highlighted that due to the nature of Varestraint test. FZ cracks only appear at the rear of the welding run. Therefore the temperature and physical state (liquid or solid) of the material placed before the central point during the application of deformation will be critical. In fact, the sample surface at this central point is the point where induced longitudinal deformations reach top value.

This effect of synchronization is not observed for the HAZ cracking phenomena since these cracks are mostly perpendicular to weld bead. In this case a comparable number of cracks and crack length were observed in the HAZ irrespectively of synchronization setup.

Finally, since different synchronization criteria induce different cracking in the FZ, the same one must be implemented if a comparable weldability assessment and hot cracking susceptibility analysis of nickel superalloys is intended. This is particularly important for castings. Otherwise, there is the risk to draw different conclusions and observe extremely different FZ cracking behavior.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn for current work:

- The magnification of the microscope is an important factor for an accurate determination of the cracks and TCL, especially in the FZ. A magnification of 150X, which is much higher than the value suggested by current testing standard lead to reduced standard deviations and lower errors and scattering induced by the measurement.
- Synchronization between welding run and deformation is also a critical testing parameter which has a direct and huge impact on TCL and MCL. Enhanced solidification cracking in the FZ is induced if bending deformation is introduced slightly before the central line. This is observed by longer cracks in FZ. Synchronization requirements are not fully defined by the testing standard and they must be known when comparing results from different machines.
- This work has enabled to define a testing and measuring procedure to reduce scattering and improve reliability on the investigation of hot cracking susceptibility of nickel superalloys. According to current results a simplified methodology based on Varestraint test using 3 augmented strains (2, 4 and 8 %) with 3 repetitions, should be enough to detect significant weldability differences between nickel superalloys with different chemical composition and/or microstructure. This will be further validated with investment casting parts.

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